

Research

The effects of Mobile IC Technology on Green Building Project Success: A Developing Country Perspective

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Accepted: 21 February , 2020; **Online:** 29 February, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3692107>

Abstract: The issue of global warming is observing everywhere to find solutions. Along with Green building project success has remained an unclear problem in construction industry. Previous study found the critical success factor for green building project success, and communication was one of the main reason. In complex age, mobile technology for information and communication have possible to increase communication and share information in the green building. However, the use of mobile technology in the form of information and communication on green building project success have not studied sufficient wisdom. A focused group meeting has arranged from nine high project professional from different construction firm in Nepal for data collection. The finding of this study as use of mobile IC technology highly influence on project success by using mobile devise, tablets and laptops. Adding more in finding, proper guidance and knowledge on mobile application and software needed to all bottom to down level employee for better project productivity. This study highlights the implication of the study and mobile IC technology on safety and health for project team as well.

Keywords: mobile technology, information & communication, green building project, project success, construction industry

1. INTRODUCTION

The building industry contributes to change in the infrastructure along with economic development and employment creation globally. However, this industry negative influence on the environment throughout construction project process such as processing, carriage of procurement, transportation and along with maintenance. As the world issue of global warming due to the environment pollution, green building projects are being highly concentrated

substance. The green building project is categorized as environmental oriented which push to make green and sustainable such as improve pureness of water, air quality, saving energy and diminution internal and external environmental pollution (Jagarajan, 2017). As Green building exploring everywhere, this is important to make green building project success in an effective way. Therefore, achieving green building project success requires top management support, leadership quality, team motivation and project managers' performance (Carvalho, 2017). In developing country Nepal, the building industry contributes eleven percent to the GDP as well as directly employs more than one million people in Nepal. However, many green building projects become failure due to delay completion, over costing, low skilled workers and slow adoption of information and communication technologies.

Green building is a complex task with multiple vendors, hence it is a critical challenge to communicate effectively between them. Although, information and communication advance technology in the form of mobile technology have drastically transformed the way of communication and sharing information in many industries (Woo, 2016). In a developing country, the nature of green building industry is different from other industry due to some features such as temporary or short-term projects, low-profit margin with high turnover, complexity nature (Fewings, 2019). Hence, limit concentration has given on mobile technology for proper communication. With the above limitation, mobile IC technology such as smartphones, laptops, mobile application, tablets, wireless network and cloud storage can help for proper communication and collaboration in green construction industry. Moreover, influencing these mobile IC technologies could help to project success in green building. Consequently, the purpose of this study to examine the use of mobile IC technology in green construction project and its inference on green building project success.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Binder (2016) communication, collaboration and management are the lifeblood of the project management. From day one to end of green building project, there are several data sharing between firms, vendors and clients, the huge number of documents created and exchanges each other with the help of mobile IC (information and communication) technology (Kibert, 2016). As per green building projects are time bounded hence, doing manual

approaches badly effects on project success including bear huge cost and loss of time in this era (Brandt, 2015).

Aktas (2015) examine that the barrier in a green building project can overcome through top management support and collaborative working with the project members so that green project can succeed. Hence, these can possible if there influence by effective mobile IC technology among project parties. Similarly, Hwang, 2015 found that 22 percent green building project in Singapore was a delay due to lack of schedule performance and lack of communication and collaboration. Moreover, based on a review of 143 articles on critical success factor for green building project success, communication and cooperation between project participants was the highest frequency cited from different literature (Li, 2019). In developed and developing country, most communication and cooperation issue such as confusion between project managers and subordinates, misunderstanding, lack of technical knowledge, low coordination, delay in responsiveness and slow decision making impacts on project success (Darko, 2016).

Most of the literature revealed that proper communication and punctuality character in information sharing is a fundamental factor for project success in green building industry (Shen, 2017). However, Yang (2007) examined that old mobile technology could not deliver the expected level of communication and information sharing. In the other side, mobile technology has capabilities to improve site work, effective information management and influence to project success on time (Anumba, 2012). Mobile devices and their applications are familiar to use on project task with more accuracy and less time spend to perform and this improves the communication and collaboration (Collins, 2015). In high advancement in software and hardware era, use of mobile IC technology has increased extremely in construction projects.

From the analysis of existing literature, it appears that the preceding scholars have mainly absorbed on mobile IC technology used in construction industry with quantitate research method. The collaboration of these mobile IC technology and their influence on green project success has not been properly examined. Therefore, our study could help to new approach on construction management with implications of the mobile IC technology on green project success.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

As per the nature of this study is exploratory, we followed a qualitative research method. According to Fellows (2015), qualitative research is suitable where research topic and research key variable new and unknown. Moreover, our study focus on mobile IC technology from the final user viewpoint and impact on project success of green building projects in developing country perspective was commenced through a focus group interview. This focus group interview is suitable with same topic to know different perspective from more interaction between focused group members (Collis, 2013).

We conducted a group session with nine highly experienced project team members from Nepalese construction industry who run their green projects. From the participation of 9 professionals, six people were above 46 years' old, five was master and above in education, six was working in a senior position. Moreover, the participants are from different sector in Nepal and they knew each other. Hence, the participants were high experience and capable of refereeing the implication of mobile technology use on green building project success. The profile of the participants is shown in **Table1**.

Table 1. Profile of focused group participants

Attributes	Classification	Frequency	Attributes	Classification	Frequency	
Age	25-35 years	1	position	site engineer (SE)	1	
	36-45 years	2		site supervisor (SS)	2	
	46-55 years	2		project managers (PM)	4	
	56-above	4		project coordinator (PC)	2	
qualification	Diploma	1	Sector	Residential Building (RB)	2	
	bachelor's degree	3		Commercial building (CB)	3	
	Master	4		Industrial building (IB)	1	
	Doctorate	1		Infrastructure project (IP)	1	
Experience	0-5 years	1	Group member code:	Transportation project (TP)	1	
	6- 10 years	1		Hydropower project (HP)	1	
	11-15 years	1		(1)SE-HP, (2)SS1-TP, (3)SS2-IP, (4)PM1-RB, (5)PM2-IB (6) PM3-CB, (7) PM4-CB, (8) PC1-RB (9)PC2-CB		
	16-20 years	2				
	21-above	4				

We asked permission to record all their discussion. The session was around one hour with three main major aspects of mobile technology and green building project success such as the type and degree of mobile technology in Nepalese construction industry, implication of mobile technology on green building project success and limitation of mobile technology.

4. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

This study coverage from focused group discussion which was the most important theme and also considered the quotes state by professional. There were four main themes such as Choice of using mobile IC technology and application; implication for green building project success, mobile IC technology influence green team behavior and use of mobile IC technology on health and safety factor. The statements from participants also used as a coding system. The code (PC1-RB) refers as project coordinator one from residential building background. In details have shown in Table 1. Only summary have described in this study which has revealed by focused group due to space limitation.

4.1 Choice of using mobile IC technology and application

Mobile device is becoming the lifeblood of communication system in every business including construction industry (Senaratne, 2016). Professional in green building project using a different kind of device such as smartphones and tablets which can work as a laptop as big screen and compatible, the participants would like to use more tablets on green project sites. It's more convenient to check and modify the electronic version documents on tablets (Svalestuen, 2017). Consequently, focus group revealed that the use of mobile device also plays an important role as per suitability in particular work. Participant SE-HP quoted that *“mostly I use my tablet to send mail due to big screen and also I use for taking pictures”*. Similarly, SS1-TP also quoted that *“as I work on road construction-site, I use mobile device for internet to use my laptop on site, some time I use my smartphone to only ready mails”*.

The function of these devices such as mobile phone, laptop and tablets are different as per situation on sites. However, the choice to use these devices affect how important and big documents are. For example, PM4-CB mentioned that *“if you using a smartphone to send some important mail which is legally considered, it can send another information that you don't want. So I suggest do not use your mobile phone to send you emails on-site”*. At that same time, PM3-

CB speaks as " *I only use my tablets or laptop on my site, I use my mobile phone only for calls, SMS and sometimes I look mails*".

We also found from group discussion that the younger project managers who have good skill in technology and educational knowledge prefer to use mobile phone. Some employees are comfortable to use and do not affect any age group. As per Nepali geographical condition, there are more difficult to get internet in every location, on that condition use of paperwork most prefer. SS2-IP quotes as " *I worked at the hilly area where there were fewer internet facilities so I like to work on paper.*" along with PM2-IB mentioned, " *whatever devices we have, we still like to use printouts*".

In the case of mobile application, we found that the project members use huge application including in-build and custom made in devices. On green project construction site weather forecast needs for work planning. Similarly, mobile camera can use for take pictures and record videos of defects build parts including making progress reports. Mobile device can share their work report with the team members and sharing best knowledge (Khelifi, 2016). According to the group discussion they used mobile technology in form of communication and information applications were Auto CAD, 3D software, and in-build application such as weather forecast, camera, GPS etc. Hence, in Nepal's green project have a very important role of mobile device to make proper communication.

4.2 Implication for green building project success

We found from focused group discussion that mobile technology form of communication and information has improved the speed of information sharing and result gives in faster decision and more comfortable within team relationship (Martin, 2019). Using their own business cloud software make simple and better for work in green project which makes concise for information sharing. As result, there has good communication between project team members. A quote was given by PM1-RB as " *I need to check the reports every day and I able to do because my team members have strong mobile technology knowledge, if there were any mistake in proposed work, we all make the best solution on time*". Also, SE-HP shared as " *I provided all the reports help from the use of mobile technology to our senior, he took decision accordance with and the project ran well*". The participants also disclosed that these technology helps to work on time, avoid misunderstanding between subordinates, improve quality, maintain the relationship between company and client in green project.

Every construction firm should complete their project within the budget with measured quality (Fewings, 2019). Since this technology has contributed to cost minimization as well from fast sharing instead of manual sharing method. With this supporting statement, PC-RB quotes that *“we use most only electronic version of documents to share in head office and no need to travel around so that it is helpful in cost minimized in the project as well”*. Although mobile technology has influenced green project success, but it depends on how they use these kinds of technology. Participants have argued that regular use of these technology impact on environment a well and influence to make eco-friendly as less paper use. Participants PC2-CB quoted as *“I received mails form bricks and sandwich panel firms about their product quality which make assurance that it not harms to environment”*. Similarly, SS1-TP included as *“I should take picture of the sites where trees are planted and I should not cut any tree as per environment rule, also if we need to cut one tree we must plant double.”*

Focused group member suggested that use of mobile technology could be more productive as well in green project. With the best proper communication, there would be good relations and maintain the data transferring on time. Hence, project team members and worker can work together in green environment. They can think about water storage, air quality, care to green tree and maintain surrounding environment if they have good communication between them. These outcomes help for project success in green building projects.

4.3 Mobile IC technology influence green team behavior

With the hot topic for hot planet, most of country promoting mobile application for green planet. For example, china has Ant Forest mobile application which help to encourage and motivate to the users for plant the tree and its success as well with millions of trees planted (Zhang, 2020). This mobile application influenced to new kind of behavior to the end user i.e. planting tree behavior. Similarly, mobile IC technology influence to the team member in green building project. A participants PM3-CB spoke as *“I always communicate to the team member for making clean environment, save water at site, do not burn any plastic on site, use proper material, should not cut any tree near to site”*. Carbon is the main reasons for environment pollution, especially for air pollution and protecting environment is a group task (Lamba, 2019). Hence, green behavior in project team directly impact to care of green environment. The focused group discussed that use of mobile IC technology is also a factor to change long term green behavior.

Participants PM1-RB quoted as *“I informed to our engineers like if workers react for any activities which harm for air, water or environment pollution, take the video or picture and inform to the team”*. Moreover, having new green behavior which protect the environment and encourage for planting the tree are part of social responsibility (Nayyar, 2016) where mobile IC technology influenced.

4.4 Use of mobile IC technology on health and safety factor

Participants highlighted the safety issue with use of mobile technology for information and communication on green project building sites. PC1-RB speaks as *“safety is more challenging when you are very busy in mobile technology, there can be a chance of an accident if you don’t look harm around”*. Similarly, some group members adding points in safety that mobile technology is adversely influenced by safety although mobile technology is very comfortable to work with a flexible place. There would be a chance of an accident if project team members are highly focused on work on site.

Participants also suggested that mobile technology harm to personal life as well. A participants PM3-CB quotes that *“sometimes I work in home in holiday with my family just due to these technology”*. With his support one more participants PM4-CB added with as *“I have to answer the mail even I went for leave for marriage ceremony”*. Consequently, use of mobile technology for information and communication impact to safety matter and personal life as well. User needs to work during holiday and can make conflict in their family life.

5. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This paper delivers some measures that construction firms can implement to make proper communication in green project by use of mobile IC technology for project success. These measures are: to find the best way to use mobile devices, both negative and positive implication on project success of green project, generates an idea for safety and health including promoting for new green behavior such as planting the tree. smartphones are friendly user for all kind of age group but due to their small screen size and internet covering issue still have limitation. Consequently, use of tablets are more used at constructing site so it is recommended that firm should find the best way to use one device instead of more device. Some devices are tough to use by team members and stay with contact, organization should arrange for training as well.

It was found that use of laptop also considered more for high important and large file. Organization should arrange the wireless internet as well. However, the mobile technology impact on personal life and health as well so organization should overlook on work-life balance. Finally, the construction site is on full of risk and most of team member and workers may not aware of safety policy while using mobile technology. It needs to be recognized for company guidelines for safety on construction sites.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In current scenario, implication of mobile IC technology on green building projects look from the view of eagle eye. Thus, the aim of this study to examine the use of mobile IC technology by project team member in green building project for project success. furthermore, this research used focused group discussion to explore the nature of green project team member towards project success. This study explored that some factor which critical factor need for green project success. Hence, the use of mobile IC technology is still to do more develop in rural area which directly impacts to project success. Green building project needs to expand these technologies as an opportunity by making different policy and instruction. However, the style of using mobile technology on construction site influence to green behavior, green project succeeds and safety as well. we consider that participant's response as interdependence, imperfect capability to examine the study as well. Moreover, the data was collected only from construction project team member in Nepalese construction industries. However, our study succeeds to find how green project team member use mobile technology and influence on green building project success. we considered only highly professional project team members as we discussed in methodology. In future, there can be qualitative and quantitate research in this area.

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Author Contributions

A.K. Collected data, performed the data analysis, drafted the paper and wrote the first draft; A.K., Y.J., M.K., and D.K. conceived and designed the study, substantially revised the manuscript and finalized the paper.

Acknowledgements

This research work was personally funded by the authors.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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